

Dr. Riccardo Fornaro
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Ref: Invitation Letter to the 17th World Congress on Computational Mechanics & 10th European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering (WCCM-ECCOMAS 2026)

Contribution/s submitted:

- A Digital Twin Framework For Sustainable Forest Management

Dear Dr. Fornaro,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we are pleased to inform you that your contribution has been accepted to be included in the Technical Programme of the **WCCM-ECCOMAS 2026 Conference**, that will take place in Munich (Germany) from **July 19 to 24, 2026**.

We sincerely appreciate your interest in participating at the Conference by presenting your contribution identified above.

Please note that final acceptance is contingent upon the payment of the conference registration fee.

We would also like to remind you that participants are responsible for arranging their own accommodation and for covering all travel and living expenses during their stay in Munich. Thank you once again for your submission and for your interest in WCCM-ECCOMAS 2026.

Sincerely,

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